

BENEFITS OF APPLYING GAMIFICATION APPROACH IN TEACHING ENGLISH TO YOUNG LEARNERS: READ ALONG (EDUCATIONAL APP)

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Abstract. This paper seeks to describe the implementation of gamification among primary school students and facilitate boosting their reading literacy and English with Read Along. Furthermore, due to the widespread use of digital technology in primary schools, gamification is gaining popularity. However, because gamified reading is new, its efficacy is not well supported by research. That is the reason we put gamification on probation with the Read Along app. This research aims at increasing pupils reading literacy through gamified strategies for primary school students. We have conducted an experiment for a month with 60 primary school students on the Read Along app. This research was implemented with two groups of students: a gamified version and the original non-gamified version. A gamified version of the group was carried out with users, points, levels, badges, and ranking. After undergoing an experiment with them, we have witnessed that the gamification affected users in different ways based on their reading literacy. The consequences of the research confirm that the gamified teaching tremendously influenced students' reading, pronunciation, and listening skills.

Keywords: gamification, Read Along app, participants, research, reading literacy.

ПРЕИМУЩЕСТВА ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ ГЕЙМИФИКАЦИИ В ОБУЧЕНИИ ЮНЫХ УЧАЩИХСЯ АНГЛИЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ: ЧИТАЙТЕ ВМЕСТЕ (ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОЕ ПРИЛОЖЕНИЕ)

Аннотация. В этой статье делается попытка описать внедрение геймификации среди учащихся начальных классов и способствовать повышению их грамотности чтения и английского языка с помощью Read Along. Кроме того, в связи с широким использованием цифровых технологий в начальных школах набирает популярность геймификация. Однако, поскольку геймифицированное чтение является новым, его эффективность недостаточно подтверждена исследованиями. Вот почему мы поставили геймификацию на испытательный срок с приложением Read Along. Это исследование направлено на повышение читательской грамотности учащихся с помощью игровых стратегий для учащихся начальных классов. В течение месяца мы проводили эксперимент с 60 учащимися начальных классов в приложении Read Along. Это исследование было реализовано с двумя группами студентов: игровая версия и исходная неигровая версия. Была проведена геймифицированная версия группы с пользователями, баллами, уровнями, значками и рейтингом. Проведя с ними эксперимент, мы увидели, что геймификация по-разному повлияла на пользователей в зависимости от их грамотности чтения. Результаты исследования подтверждают, что геймифицированное обучение оказало огромное влияние на навыки чтения, произношения и аудирования учащихся.

Ключевые слова: геймификация, приложение Read Along, участники, исследование, читательская грамотность.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, gamification is becoming available in every field of education. In the 21st century, it has started its own initiative to enhance the effectiveness of lessons in teaching. Gamified instruction increases interest in books and classes while assisting all sorts of students in moving forward and succeeding in the classroom. When used in conjunction with the Read Along app, it is regarded as one of the most effective methods and strategies to increase the effectiveness of reading literacy. Additionally, the inclusion of gaming features in a classroom environment is known as "gamification of education," a strategy for increasing participation.[1] The major goals of this technique are to improve specific skills that learners must have. In the teaching of English, gamified instruction is important. Delivering the lessons with a crucial and powerful strategy can lead our offspring to be well-educated and well-qualified. Critical thinking is considered one of the most important skills for increasing reading comprehension and literacy. After acquiring sufficient reading proficiency, students may become motivated to read more books throughout their lives. Numerous educational professionals contend that pupils' comprehension increases as they read more. A study by Becker et al. showed that reading interest has continuing positive effects on reading achievement.[2]

METHODS

At the beginning of the experimentation, the primary school students were given the opportunity to experiment with the research about gamification in reading. They were the participants in the third grade, and the total number of pupils was sixty. The students were separated into two groups and started experimenting with them. The research goal was accomplished using the gamified version of the group. The experiment was repeatedly conducted on the experimental group. Before conducting the probation, I took a test about their reading skills and knowledge. During their one-month duration, I observed them carefully and put useful and powerful strategies based on gamification into the pupil's hands to increase their reading skills. Particularly, their tests were based on the Read Along app. This app provided them with everything they needed to learn about reading. Having finished one month of research on them, all of the details of probation were accounted for. At the end of the day, two groups were compared according to their results. The experimental group achieved a dramatic upheaval and gained skills that were extremely vital to them.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. RESULTS

Scores were compared between groups in order to improve reading literacy using the Read Along app.

Before the experiment			After the experiment	
S	1-group	2-group	A gamified version group	Non-gamified version group
R	40.5	39.7	88.5	40.7
P	32.5	33.7	82.7	30.2

L	32.5	35	82.9	30
S	27.7	27.6	75.8	27.6
T	33.3	34	82.475	33.375

S – SKILL

R – READING

P – PRONUNCIATION

L – LISTENING

S – SPEAKING

Table 1 illustrates that there was no growth in reading with this controversial study. Two groups had low scores and virtually remained stable at 34 percent. That means that there was no interest in reading. In the second table, you can see the research that contributed to increasing the number of bookworms in educational environments. Because of the Read Along app and its utilization among primary school pupils. After putting it up as an experiment, there was a big upheaval between the two groups. The gamified group pupils achieved success, while the original, non-gamified group students leveled off at 33.375 percent. All in all, the research indicates that there was a rocket increase when two groups compared each other.

B. DISCUSSION

Students in primary schools were asked to focus their research on one particular area. In order to improve reading literacy among children at a young age, the research sought to address the issue with them. In order to improve pupils' reading abilities, this study used Read Along. The experiment's findings were observed and obtained over the course of a month. The students were provided readings based on their level and knowledge while the experiment was taking place. The students were required to be taught via gamification before the research was conducted. Gamification was included into teaching and learning activities in accordance with the Read Along app's recommendations. They were instructed on how to utilize Read Along and complete tasks in it during the activity process. They were able to see the stories and exercises. The app has entertaining stories, games, and activities that are based on texts so that users can comprehend their meaning. This app has its own narrator, and she guides pupils to implement tasks. This platform lists the following fundamental aspects of the app: user, challenge, point, level, badges, and ranking. During that probation, they were required to follow the instructions that the narrator gave them. At the beginning of the experiment, they utilized the Read Along app stories as games. After the narrator ceased telling the story, they had to begin the texts. They faced various difficulties when using this software and earned points for taking part in the game, regardless of how well they performed. They may level up to a high position in the game after gaining points, and as a reward, they would receive badges for their involvement. Based on how well they performed in completing the task, they were offered these incentives. They will receive three stars if they give it their all or do the work flawlessly; but, if the points are in the other direction, they will not be considered the game's victor.

Students could be engaged and active in class after applying gamification using Read Along. Students frequently excelled in the Read Along app when they took part in reading instruction, which served as proof. Gamification produces improved learning experiences as it combines fun and learning while using the app game.

Through the Read Along gamification method, the students' results showed that they were better able to comprehend and assimilate the stories and lessons through the Read Along app than through a traditional test. Additionally, it enhanced for them their reading, pronunciation, listening, and speaking abilities. The participant must next repeat the text with the proper pronunciation once the narrator has first read it out. They learnt how to properly pronounce the words they heard when they listened to the narrator's account. It consequently improved hearing, reading, and pronunciation abilities. After wrapping up the narrative in enjoyable activities and poignant ways, they had a wealth of speaking subject suggestions. At the end of the day, they answered the questions in an excellent way.

Gamification has made a significant contribution to pupils' increased interest in reading, because of the carefully curated games and stories in the Read Along app. According to Wigfield et al. reading interest plays an important role in helping students comprehend the text because it is a fundamental factor that is directly related to their reading goals.¹ The scholar's aforementioned statement about providing intriguing topics based on their preferences is spot on, and it would be preferable to maintain consistency in reading more books with the gamification method. Scientists are now incorporating gamified teaching techniques into reading-based activities to increase desirable activities. Our study showed that adopting gamified teaching techniques in conjunction with the intriguing stories in the Read Along app had a significant impact. Additionally, with the assistance of the elementary school pupils, we successfully completed our experiment and obtained the desired reading outcome.

CONCLUSION

The Read Along gamification project gave participants the best opportunities and results in their educational setting. Gamification has been implemented, and it has had a substantial impact on how well users can read. You will gradually improve your speaking and listening abilities by participating in this probation. The inferential analysis of this research revealed that group students who were gamified experienced much more growth than group students who were not gamified.

The results of the investigation showed that although the reading scores of the original group stayed consistent at around 34%, those of the gamified version group changed. The final results of the gamified set of students shot up from 33.3 to 82.475 percent.

It has successfully exposed the courses' outcomes by structuring the teachings in funny and relevant ways. These kind of apps can be used to prepare lessons that will improve the students' reading abilities. In order to develop an educational atmosphere in learners' lives nowadays, education must be clear and precise for them. Therefore, in order to increase readership, teachers and tutors must plan classes using a gamified teaching approach for every type of learner.

REFERENCES

1. A. Wigfield, J.S. Eccles, J.A. Fredricks, and S. Simpkins, 'Development of Achievement Motivation and Engagement,' vol. 3, pp. 657-700, 2015.
2. M. BECKER, N. McElvany, and M. Kortenbruck, 'Intrinsic and Extrinsic Reading Motivation as Predictors of Reading Literacy: A Longitudinal Study,' J. Educ. Psychol., vol. 102, pp. 773-785, 2010.

3. <https://bera-journals.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/bjet.13057>
4. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/09588221.2021.1939388?scroll=top&needAccess=true&role=tab&aria-labelledby=full-article>
5. <https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.google.android.apps.seekh&referrer=inapp>
6. https://www.pointagram.com/gamification/?gclid=Cj0KCQjw6cKiBhD5ARIsAKXUdyYiJGSdfdAzjG6OnG0dLSO0n6fu7UeVH3ax-GceFIFH4qk0wo1XfYaAvRFEALw_wcB